

**PHILOSOPHICAL APPRAISAL OF DIVINE HEALING AND ITS
IMPLICATIONS FOR CHRISTIAN MISSIONARY EXPANSION IN NIGERIA:
“PENTICOSTALISM”.**

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Abstract

Historical records have revealed the philosophical appraisal of divine healing and its implications for Christian missionary expansion in Nigeria. Christians emphasized divine healing as a direct experience of God's power through the Holy Spirit to heal the sick. This comment, however, faced criticism and exposed occasional frauds, thus prompting philosophical inquiries into God's existence; the challenge of evil in the world, and the credibility of miracles within Pentecostal context. Hence, the research analyzed Christians' beliefs and practices on divine healing, exploring its philosophical dimensions and practical implications for social and religious dynamics. Data were collected through historical and descriptive survey methods, participant observation and oral interviews with pastors and members. The study explored Epicurus and J.L. Mackie's works on the problem of evil, and David Hume's skepticism regarding miracles. Here, divine healing is viewed as divine intervention, while sickness is viewed as evil and natural occurrence. Findings indicated that, all surveyed Christian Churches in Nigerian considered divine healing as genuine act of God and practice it as their central doctrine. Conclusively, the study

identified positive and negative impacts of divine healing on Christian missionary expansion in Nigeria, as this strengthening faith, unity and spiritual empowerment. It caused over-reliance on faith and generated arguments on its genuineness among Christian denominations. Therefore, promotion of interdenominational dialogue and Church leadership education on pragmatic practices of divine healing, transparency and accountability are recommended for church growth. The aftermath and misconception on divine healing should periodically address to prove divine healing as genuine act of God.

Keywords: Christianity, Divine Healing, Belief in Miracle, Diseases, Sickness

Introduction

Inarguably, Christianity in Nigeria thrives on claims of solving human existential problems through the power of God. Its claim includes divine healing for all manner of sicknesses and diseases. In fact, it often connects most sicknesses and diseases to demonic afflictions, propels the drive to invoke divine power of the Holy Spirit to heal the sick through different forms of prayers. Whereas, they are aware of natural sicknesses and diseases which etiologically have scientific explanations, and not connected with witchcraft or demonic afflictions; they sometimes jettison medical treatment for miraculous interventions through faith and prayer. Divine healing as a miraculous act of God through the Holy Spirit is replete in the Bible and Pentecostal as one of the Christian movements' in Nigeria has a history of promoting it as an enchanted religion. It is common knowledge that from the North America, Pentecostal preachers such as Alexander Dowie, Kathryn Kuhlman, Oral Robert, Gordon Lindsay, Kenneth Haggin, Morris Cerullo, Reinhard Bonke, Benny Hinn, and a host of others were being seen on the global Pentecostal stage, performing healings in their various televised healing meetings and crusades. While these preachers were not initiators of Pentecostalism in Africa; their influence on its development is substantial.

Pentecostalism in Africa can be traced to the uncompromising faith in divine healing. Among the Yoruba for instance, the prayer group, named Precious Stone group broke away from the Anglican Church, at Ijebu-Ode, during the bubonic influenza in 1918. It metamorphosed into a Pentecostal movement named Precious Cornerstone Church, as a result of its excommunication as a prayer group due to doctrinal controversy (Ijaola, 27). From its initial affiliation to Faith Tabernacle Congregation and later to the classical Pentecostal group of British Apostolic Church, divine healing was extremely emphasized and became a cardinal

doctrine of The Apostolic Church Nigeria. The doctrine also features even in the breakaway denominations such as the Christ Apostolic Church, Nigeria (Fatokun et al, 54). Similarly, the American Neo-Pentecostal influenced preachers and denominations that burgeon from 1971 in Nigeria including: Benson Idahosa Church of God Mission, Redeemed Christian Church of God and others spread the practice of divine healing through discipleship, televangelism and crusades all across Africa. Thus, besides the acclaimed diseases associated with witchcraft and sorcery, which are considered to be beyond scientific solution, knowledge deficit and poverty are some of the reasons people patronizes divine healing in Pentecostal settings (Olukunke, 1).

As divine healing represents an act of miraculous intervention by a Deity; sickness and diseases represents evil in the world (Olatubi, 91). Interestingly, the duo has generated serious arguments against theistic belief in the existence of God. Furthermore, the uncompromising stand of theists on the divine attributes of God as omnipresent, omniscient and omnibenevolent reinforces the controversies. Since evil is anything that causes pain and suffering, sickness is a typical example of this human existential realities as regarded to evil (Olatubi, 93). In the context of Pentecostalism, divine healing, has been a kind faith practice for millions of believers across the world. The promise of miraculous healing, as evident in the New Testament accounts of Jesus' ministry and the early Christian church, continues to inspire hope and devotion in Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria today.

The complexities and nuances of the practices of divine healing have also raised sparking debates within Pentecostals circles and the public. From suspected foul play, exaggerated claims, mistrust in science and alternative medicine to obstruction to seeking or delivering medical treatment; claims of divine healing stirred public discuss in Nigeria. It is on this note that, this study appraises the belief in divine healing with the view to examine its implications for Church missionary expansion in Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

The idea of divine healing generated concerns about the problem of evil, because the omniscient, omnipotent and Omnibenevolent God should not heal people but eradicate disease and sicknesses. Philosophers such as Epicurius and Mackie have generated unending debates on the subject of problem of evil. On the other hand, it raises questions on the reasonableness of

miracles as generated by David Hume. While scholars have examined the idea of divine healing from both sides of problem of evil and reasonableness of miracles, there is obvious need to further expound research on church members' beliefs in divine healing due to various claims and counter claims of divine healings among Christians in Nigeria, hence this research.

Research Questions

The following questions raised in order to tackle these Problems:

- i. what do Christians believe about divine healing in Nigerian Churches?
- ii. how do Christians (Pentecostalism) practice divine healing in Nigerian Churches?
- iii. are there philosophical arguments for and against divine healing in the light of Christians' beliefs and practices in Nigerian Churches?
- iv. what are the implications of the belief in divine healing on Nigeria Christians Churches?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study examined belief in divine healing and its implications among Christian Churches in Nigerian. The objectives of the research were to:

- i. analyze Christian's beliefs of divine healing in Nigerian Churches.
- ii. examine the practices of divine healing among Christian Churches in Nigeria.
- iii. interrogate the philosophical arguments for and against divine healing in the light of Christians' beliefs and practices in Nigerian Churches.
- iv. explain the implications of the idea of divine healing on Nigeria Christians Churches.

Research Methods

This research adopted historical and descriptive survey methods and examined past events regarding divine healing in Pentecostalism, one of the Christian Churches in Nigeria, with the use of primary and secondary sources of data collection. Instruments used are participant observation and oral interviews to some of the Pentecostalism churches in Nigeria.

This method involves several key steps to ensure the accurate and critical analysis of historical data. The Primary sources are first-hand accounts and direct evidence from the period being studied. While Secondary Sources: include analyses, interpretations and summaries of historical events created by other researchers or historians. Descriptive survey method in the other hand is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from few people. The populations of this study consist of all the Pentecostals Churches in Nigeria, while seven selected Classical and Neo-Pentecostal churches were considered as the sample of the study, these includes; The Apostolic Church Nigeria, Christ Apostolic Church, Deeper Life Church, Mountain of Fire and Miracle, Redeemed Christian Church of God, Living Faith Church and Christ embassy Church. The Sampling Techniques consists of (28) total numbers of respondents. (Two) Pastors and (Two) members from the seven selected denominations were orally interviewed who provided reliable data from diverse perspectives and experiences related to the beliefs and Practices of divine healing in their denominations. Their responses on the beliefs and practices of divine healing were recorded and written down. The data collected were structured, interpreted and analyzed. The oral interview is divided into two sections namely A and B: Section (A) contained the interviewee's personal data such as name, gender, age, denomination, and office(s) held. Section (B) contained 22 interview questions basically on: the Pentecostal beliefs and practices of divine healing, Philosophical arguments for and against the belief and practice of divine healing and its implication for Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria.

Review of Relevant Literature

Scholars have written on the idea of divine healing; hence, this research explores various relevant literatures related to divine healing. The subject of divine healing is vast and quite controversial, in the sense that some Christians were confused over the way it should have worked in their lives. Research through participant interview had revealed that, some Christians believed that one thing is sure, that it is God's will for His people to be healed. So, they are of the believe that they must be healed since they belong to the same God through adoption and by grace. Anyway, this is clearly revealed in many passages of the Bible. What is not always clear is why so many Christians who do seek God at the same time believe in his divine power were not healed (Questions Ministries, 2022). It is often stated in the context of Pentecostal beliefs that

many sufferers from sickness lack divine healing because of their lack of faith in God's will to heal them (Francis, 14). Another point of view opines that, "divine healing in Pentecostal Churches hinges on the name of Jesus Christ and faith in his healing power" (Owooye, 104). Healing, as claimed by Christianity, comes as a result of the power of the Holy Spirit. It is also referred to as anointing, that breaks the yoke of the devil (Owooye, 104). Notwithstanding, certain questions continue to agitate people's minds as to why it is that many people who seek to be healed of their ailments are not, this leads to recourse to the supernatural; when there are good orthodox hospitals around for them to be healed. However, Meyer opined that:

Pentecostal Churches distinguish between the physical realm and the spiritual realm. The spiritual realm to them determines what goes on in the visible world. Sickness and misfortune are understood to be a result of spiritual evil intruding into a person's spirit and body. Therefore, all over the world there is a spiritual war going on between God and the devil, thus Pentecostal preachers claim to be able to penetrate the invisible through prayers to bring about physical healing to their members, (Meyer, 98).

Therefore, it was discovered that, in divine healing is becoming very little in the Pentecostal Churches based on two reasons; one, great numbers of people think that miracles as well as gifts of healing are limited to the time of the primitive Church, that their object was to establish the first foundation of Christianity, but from that time circumstances have altered. Two, the Church has lost the gifts of healing by her own fault; because she has become worldly that the Spirit acts in her has not remained in direct and habitual relationship with the full power of God. Therefore, if the Church were to see anew springing up within her men and women who live the life of faith and of the Holy Spirit, entirely consecrated to their God, she would see again the manifestation of the same gifts as in former times (Murray, 3).

Consequently, there has been a reserve to abandon the belief that it is God's will to heal the sick. This has caused tensions in Pentecostal belief and practice on divine healing, and the distinction between God's will and the desire to be healed is often blurred. Christians who suffered physically or mentally, their presence within some Pentecostal environments has sat

awkwardly in the context of a perceived belief that healing is available for all, this is sole to Pentecostalism and is substantially increasing in the context of Pentecostal belief and practice (Warrington, 46). The healings of Jesus are still referred to in many prayers for the sick and appealed to as a major basis for believing that similar healings are expected for all believers today. However, the link between the healing ministry of Jesus and that of contemporary believers is still assumed not happening as supposed to, though this is not always clarified, but the absence of divine healing is often inadequately addressed as there is little or no result to show in many cases among the Pentecostal Churches today (Warrington, 46).

Concept of Divine Healing

The idea of divine healing can be found among various religious traditions including; Christianity, Islam, Hinduism, Buddhism, and other religions of the world. It stems from the belief that the divine or the supernatural being called God is compassionate, loving, and has the power to intervene in humans' suffering and pain. In Christianity, divine healing refers to the belief and practice of seeking healing through supernatural means, often attributed to God and it is being rooted in biblical teachings, particularly in passages such as James 5:14-15, which instruct believers to pray for the sick and anoint them with oil in the name of the Lord for healing. This forms the theological basis for many Pentecostal and charismatic practices (Anderson, 45). Divine healing is being defined as a "means of restoring health through a direct intervention of God through prayer of faith, laying on of hands and anointing with oil".

Origin of Sicknesses and Diseases

In Christianity the origin of sickness is termed to be the result of man's sin of disobedient as recorded in Genesis 3, and Israel's disobedience to God's commandments in the wilderness as the main causes of the outbreaks of diseases and suffering in the world (Exodus 15:26 and Deuteronomy 28:15-22). According to (Kumuyi, 28), "Sin Causes sickness" and that the first record of sickness came as a result of personal sin Gen 20:1-18, remarkably the healing of this sickness was an answer to prayer. Dowie opined that, "Sickness is the foul offspring of Satan", Sickness therefore is not the will of God rather it is the product of sin, (Moore, 45).

According to (Akindele, 8), “sickness is a result of the broken and fallen nature of man and therefore presumed that it is a consequence of man’s sinful nature which led him to imperfection. (Osborn, 9) agreed with Akindele that Sickness is not natural; rather it was caused by man’s sin that, God made all things very good and perfect. Therefore, man should not look for the remedy of sickness in the natural, but from God who created him happily, strong, and healthy. Babalola is in the opinion that, “sickness, is a punishment for man’s sin and that with the forgiveness available in Christ’s atonement, sin and sicknesses would be removed from the lives of the Christians who claim the benefit”, (Folarin, 94).

From the above points of view; according to Akindele, Osborn and Folarin, “sickness is the result and punishment of man’s sinful acts”. However, if Man’s sin was the result of his suffering, in the contrary it is against the claim of God by Osborn as one who created everything good and perfect. If God created everything perfect, how does man whom God created in his own image identify with imperfection to the point of sinning against his original form? From the philosophical point of view, therefore God himself must be an imperfect being lacking one of his Characters as claimed to be by theism. This is argued by the logical form of the problem of evil in the world, “God who is all-powerful, all-knowing, and wholly good exists at the same time evil exist in our world. This is logically inconsistency, is not possible that God exists and is omnipotent, omniscient, and wholly good and evil exists at the same time” (Rowe, 112). Keith argued with Rowe that “it is the will of God for all people to be healed today if there had never been any sin, and there wouldn’t have been any sickness or death or any such evils. As it is written in the Bible the consequences of sin are death and that cannot be the will of God” (Moore, 45).

In Christianity, causes of sicknesses and diseases are mostly referred to either man’s sin or demon’s attack. Augustine opines that sickness in Christianity is seen as demons attack (Rowe, 133).

Interplay between Divine Healing, Orthodox, and Alternative Medicine

Today, many people use a combination of divine healing, orthodox medicine, and alternative therapies. For example, a patient might receive chemotherapy (orthodox) while also praying for recovery (divine) and using acupuncture to manage side effects which is (alternative). Conflicts and Synergies: There can be conflicts when religious beliefs contradict medical advice, such as refusing blood transfusions for religious reasons. However, there are also synergies where spiritual practices support mental and emotional well-being during conventional treatment. The use of Medicine in Pentecostal history has been viewed as suspicious and negative form of healing and inappropriate for believers (Keith, 46). This belief has however significantly decreased in recent decades, most Pentecostal denomination had recognized that all healings have divine origin, therefore the use of orthodox medicine/alternative is now appropriate for all Christians. In the present time, the popular view in Pentecostalism is in dialogue and integration with medical practices, the use of medicine is no longer taken as a sin by believers in Christ Jesus.

Science versus Miracle

The modern period of philosophy is referred to as the period of inquiry, in which scholars turn away from fetishism, dogmatism, subjectivism, magic, etc., to rationalism and empiricism. Thus, scientific investigations became the backbone of the modern way of thought; the universe is now a vast set of facts that can be known through scientific investigations (Ngamen, 47). The debate between science and miracles involves a clash between naturalistic explanations and supernatural claims. Science relies on empirical evidence and repeatability, while miracles are often seen as one-time events that defy natural laws. This inquiry explores arguments from both perspectives. In Pentecostalism belief, many have thought it necessary to posit spiritual, nonscientific reasons and explanations for certain events that occur in the world, which include various claims of miracles and various kinds of religious experiences (Meister, 79). Some people maintained that they have been miraculously healed or had a religious experience of one sort or the other. It is worth to note that; medical science had also gained ground with primary, secondary and tertiary health facilities all over the world challenging the authentic of divine healing as embraced by Pentecostalism. However, despite the advancement of science and

technology on medical care (Newell, 2) opines that, “miraculous healing is still in place till today,” to him, modern medicine cannot and does not always bring about healing, that even most physicians recognize the value of prayer, for which many at times result to healings beyond their understanding; some refer to these healings as miracle.

Science is based on the consistency and predictability of natural laws. These laws, derived from empirical observation, provide a framework for understanding the universe (Hawking, Stephen, and Leonard Mlodinow, 109). Science has its limitations and cannot explain everything. Some phenomena may genuinely be beyond natural explanation (Polkinghorne, 90). If the supernatural exists, as many religious traditions claim, then miracles are possible and science cannot fully account for them (Lewis, 145). Some argue that science and miracles are not mutually exclusive but can be complementary, with miracles occurring within a broader divine framework (Barbour, 57). The tension between science and miracles is an enduring philosophical and theological debate. Science emphasizes empirical evidence, repeatability, and natural laws, while proponents of miracles argue from testimony, divine action, philosophical justification, and historical evidence. Each perspective has strengths and weaknesses, and the debate continues to evolve with ongoing advancements in both scientific and philosophical understanding.

Magic and its Confusion with Miracle

Miracles and magic have fascinated humanity for millennia, serving as crucial elements in religious, cultural, and philosophical narratives. While miracles are typically associated with divine intervention and religious significance, magic is often linked to occult practices and the manipulation of supernatural forces. This exploration delves into the distinctions, similarities, and philosophical implications of miracles and magic. Magic involves the use of rituals, symbols, and actions to manipulate supernatural force. Unlike miracles, magic is often viewed as a practice or technique that can be learned and controlled (Frazer, 15). Magic has played a significant role in various cultures, often intertwined with religion, medicine, and early science (Thomas, 45). Philosophers and anthropologists examine magic as a worldview distinct from scientific and religious paradigms, often emphasizing its symbolic and psychological

dimensions (Tambiah, 102). Contemporary views often reinterpret magic through the lenses of psychology and cultural studies, exploring its relevance in modern society (Styers, 201).

Miracles are typically acts of divine will, while magic involves human agency manipulating supernatural forces. Both concepts challenge naturalistic understandings of the world (Kieckhefer, 89). Miracles are often revered within religious contexts, whereas magic can be viewed with suspicion or as heretical. In some cultures, the line between miracle and magic can be blurred (Flint, 134). Miracles have more to do with hope, healing, deliverance and revealing God's love. Robert, in his own opinion states that "Magic is the intentional effort to have us believe that what we see and experience is real, when it isn't, while a miracle is the intentional effort to have us believe that what we see and experience is real. Shayne, differentiates magic from miracle thus; in magic, a person tries to manipulate an outcome while in a miracle, spoken words backed with authority produce results. Joey Evans adds that, no matter how incredible the feat of "magic" one performs, it can be explained by natural means and could be shown how it is done.

Most people wrongly take miracle as magic; in Christianity the spiritual powers to perform healing depend on God and do not agree with magic where forces are manipulated to perform something unusual. Supernatural power for healing lies at the core of both miracles and magic. According to Regina Brett, "Magic and miracles are similar in that they are both used to describe how powerful God works in our lives (Brett, 96). Thus, magic and miracles are everywhere. People generally believe in the reality of diseases and sicknesses; they however differ on the idea of magic or miracle for healing. Magic is one of the means of healing especially in African traditional religion (ATR). Traditional healing among various cultural groups in Nigeria use magic as alternative medicine for healing, however; a number of persons, especially Christians patronize, prayer houses, miracle centers, and crusade meetings seeking for divine healing, (Fuller, 82).

Philosophical Appraisal of Divine Healing

Divine healing, particularly within Pentecostal contexts, is a significant and often contentious aspect of religious belief and practice. This appraisal aims to examine the philosophical underpinnings, implications, and controversies surrounding the practice of divine healing. Philosophical discourse on divine healing engages with classical theistic arguments, particularly the attributes of God as omnipotent, omniscient, and omnibenevolent. This raises significant questions about the problem of evil and the nature of miracles. Philosophical appraisal of divine healing involves examining the concept from a rational and critical perspective. Divine healing raises questions such as; if God has the power to heal, why does He allow suffering and illness in the first place? This philosophical dilemma challenges the notion of divine healing as a consistent and universal phenomenon. Philosophers had in both ancient and recent time seek rational explanations of various religious beliefs such as miracles. Epicurus and J.L. Mackie's formulation of the problem of evil challenges the coherence of believing in a benevolent and all-powerful deity in the face of pervasive suffering and sickness. If God can prevent illness but does not, this seems to contradict His benevolence or omnipotence.

Pentecostal responses often posit that sickness results from human free will or demonic influence, thus preserving divine benevolence and omnipotence (Mackie, 200).

Sickness as one of the evils existential reality which ravages the world left many people in pain and discomfort. Some believers of God especially Christians are with a question that is yet to be answered by the theism. People do ask “why me, why am I suffering, why am I in pain, am I not serving God enough, who has the power to deliver me from every calamity, what is the matter? Suppose there does exist all powerful, all knowing, all loving and everywhere at the same time should have deliver his people from every evil facing them. Thus, the existence of God is philosophically argued this way:

God who is all knowing should know when evil is about to happen in the world, and, as all powerful, God should prevent evil from happening and all loving God should not allow evil to have occurred especially on those who believe in his existence and fully serve him faithfully. But the reality of evil in the world is of

no doubt; therefore, philosophically God, arguably, does not exist or he exists but does not possess his attribute as he is being described by theism (Chad, 63).

Stephan argues that, “divine healing is not a reality or, if it is, perhaps only God determines who will be healed”. If that is indeed the case, does it mean that the believer's prayer is in vain? Therefore some reject divine healing as fiction, lacking any basis in reality, while others recognize that there may be some truth in it. While many views the reports of divine healing as an exaggeration of what is not really happening today. Some believe that the absence of divine healing is an indication of lack of faith on the part of the believer, (Precious, 65). Philosophical appraisal of divine healing is based on the contention that the healing practiced by miraculous healers is nothing more than a 'mind-over-matter' approach, leading people into confessing over and over that they will be healed, but everyone is not healed through the confession. More alarming are attempts from within the Christian faith itself to focus on human potential for health, thus moving the focus from ethnocentric providence to anthropocentric health. Advocates of the prosperity gospel claim that it is God's will for every believer to be prosperous and healthy (Sarles, 329). The implication is that a sick or poor person finds himself/herself outside God's will with regard to his or her life.

David Hume's skepticism about miracles further complicates the belief in divine healing. Hume argues that miracles are violations of natural laws and thus inherently improbable. For Hume, the evidence for a miracle must be extraordinarily strong to outweigh the inherent improbability of such events (Hume, 115). Pentecostals counter this by emphasizing the experiential and communal aspects of faith, where personal and collective experiences of healing serve as compelling evidence. Empirical scrutiny of divine healing claims often reveals inconsistencies and unverified assertions. Reports of failed healings and instances of fraudulent practices undermine the credibility of divine healing. Nevertheless, the enduring belief in such healings among Pentecostals in Nigeria points to the profound psychological and social functions of these beliefs. The tension between divine healing and medical science is another critical area of philosophical inquiry. Olatubi opines that, the tension between divine healing and medical science is partly traditional and metaphysical, as the issue of divine healing goes beyond one's choice of head (*Ori-eni*) from creation, either good or bad head, divine healing

intervention can cure it and turn such head for better in life. While some Pentecostals eschew medical treatment in favour of prayer, others adopt a more integrative approach, acknowledging the benefits of both spiritual and medical interventions. This pragmatic stance aligns with a broader philosophical perspective that recognizes the limitations and potentialities of both faith and reason.

The belief in divine healing also carries significant implications for Pentecostal practice in Nigeria. It fosters a sense of hope and empowerment among adherents, particularly in a context where access to advanced medical care is limited. However, it also raises ethical concerns about the potential neglect of medical treatments and the exploitation of vulnerable individuals. Divine healing is also being appraised through Placebo effect and natural healing. A placebo is a substance or treatment that has no therapeutic effect, often used in clinical trials to test the efficacy of new medications or treatments. The concept of the placebo is central to the placebo effect, where patients experience real changes in their health or symptoms simply because they believe they are receiving treatment (Benedetti, 1-34). When examining claims of divine healing, it is important to consider alternative explanations, such as the placebo effect or natural healing processes. Are the reported of healings truly miraculous, or could they be attributed to psychological factors or the body's inherent ability to heal itself.

Ethical and Cultural considerations: Divine healing has ethical implications, particularly when it comes to medical decisions. Should individuals solely rely on divine healing and reject medical treatments? Balancing faith and wisdom in seeking healing raises ethical questions about the responsibility of individuals to take care of their health and the potential consequences of disregarding medical advice as some individual die as a result of their faith that deny them the opportunity to consult medical cure. **Cultural and contextual factors:** It is crucial to recognize that beliefs in divine healing are often influenced by cultural and contextual factors. Different religious traditions and cultural backgrounds may shape how divine healing is understood and practiced.

Practice of Divine Healing among Contemporary Pentecostal Churches

The practice of divine healing is common among Pentecostal Churches, below are some of the practice of divine healing: (i) Intercession prayer and laying of hands, (ii) Faith healing, (iii) Anointing oil, (iv) Faith Clinic and Deliverance, and (v) Revival and Testimonies Services.

Issues Regarding the Beliefs in Divine Healing

Right from 1986, certain fundamental spiritual changes began to take place in Christianity other than the way it used to be perceived and practiced in Nigeria, and other parts of West Africa. This was through the rise of Charismatic Pentecostal movements. This new religious way was referred to as revivalist movement within Pentecostal churches with global dimension. From the early twentieth century, by the 1990s Pentecostalism moved into public domain to become a global religion, thus attracted the attention of generality of the Christians and non-Christians (Ojo, 75). Pentecostal churches believe in the power of divine healing, emphasizing that it is a direct result of the ministry of Jesus Christ and the work of the Holy Spirit. They often base this belief on biblical passages such as James 5:14-15, which encourages believers to pray for healing and anoint the sick with oil. These issues include; faith and expectation, variations in practice, healing as God wills, false claims and exploitation and psychosomatic effects.

Findings:

The findings of this research are:

1. That all Pentecostal churches had beliefs in divine healing and combined divine healing with medical treatment, but Christians should prioritize hygienic life to avoid falling sick.
2. Pentecostal Churches are examining the practices of divine healing with prayer and fasting, laying of hands, anointing oil, deliverance and using of handkerchiefs or mantles.
3. From Christian perspective, it is logical to believe in miracles and divine healing, but from Philosophical point of view it is not logical to believe in divine healing and miracle.

4. By explaining the implications of the idea of divine healing on Christian (Pentecostal) Churches in Nigeria, divine healing increases church population, strengthens faith, encourages a deeper spiritual connection and trust in God's power and promote community bonds. In the contrary divine healing leads to over-reliance on faith healing and expectations of miraculous interventions.

Conclusion: The study revealed a strong belief in divine healing and its implications on Nigerian Christian (Pentecostal) churches, with variations in how it is practiced, influenced and integrated into members' lives. Personal testimonies highlight the perceived efficacy of divine healing, while attitudes towards medical treatment vary, ranging from prioritizing faith to embracing both faith and medical care. The practices of divine healing among Pentecostal churches are characterized by a strong reliance on prayer, anointing with oil, and communal faith-building exercises which aftermath influenced the church positively. Each church has distinct methods but shares a common emphasis on God's power to heal through faith.

Recommendations: This study, therefore, offers the following recommendation that: Christian (Pentecostal) Churches should train Pastors to understand the biblical basis and practical implications of divine healing; Church leaders should adapt to balanced approaches to healing that integrate faith practices with medical treatments, promoting holistic health and well-being of their members; Churches should facilitate interdenominational programmes to work on best mode of practice of divine healing among Christian denominations to promote mutual understanding on how to ensuring transparency and accountability in its; and Provide Counseling Services in the churches to give room for individuals and families to decide about their health care choices on both spiritual and medical interventions.

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